

Using baited remote underwater videos (BRUV) and interviews with knowledge holders to assess reef passage fish species around Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025 Study report

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1. Introduction to the project and research context

Reef passages are natural breaks in reefs that connect the coastal zones to the open ocean. As hotspots for biodiversity, reproductivity, and as pathways for fisher(wo)men as well as a variety of non-human species, they hold remarkable value for environment and society.

The project SOCPacific2R designs its research activities using an empirical inter- and transdisciplinary approach, combining natural and social sciences methods, and focuses on reef passages in Fiji and New Caledonia. The project aims to:

1. Conducting a transdisciplinary study of reef passages as under-researched features of social-ecological coral reef systems that constitute complex, interconnected, and dynamic assemblages of living and non-living, dwelling and transiting, entities that interact with each other;
2. Documenting both area-based and other management and conservation arrangements applied to reef passages, including the pros and cons that local stakeholder groups identify;
3. Establishing a participatory science-society-policy dialogue informed by social-ecological studies, Oceanian socio-cosmologies and sovereignties, and governance norms in/for the management and conservation of reef passages.

SOCPacific2R works with various stakeholders to achieve the project's goals: scientists, administrators, NGOs, and local communities. The outcomes of the project will feed into wider frameworks on marine sustainability such as the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Local communities are the main knowledge holders and users of the reef passages that surround the Fijian and New Caledonian islands. The presented study aimed to learn their perspectives and experiences concerning the reef passages on Ovalau island in Fiji through an interdisciplinary research team, and was conducted by a student group of the University of the South Pacific (USP) between September 2025 and February 2026.

Reef passages in Fiji function as ecologically dynamic corridors that facilitate fish movement between lagoonal and oceanic habitats, particularly during tidal exchanges (Breckwoldt et al. 2022). These systems are also culturally and economically significant, serving as key fishing grounds for coastal communities. Despite their importance, reef passages remain underrepresented in quantitative biodiversity surveys relative to reef flats and outer reef slopes. This dataset addresses that gap by providing standardized, non-extractive observations of reef-associated fauna in high-current passage environments.

2. Research Methodology

The main aim of this project was to assess reef passage fish diversity and abundance around Ovalau island, Fiji, using baited remote underwater videos (BRUVs) in reef passages and integrating local ecological knowledge (LEK) gained from semi-structured interviews with fishermen (Figure 1). The participants in this study were exclusively male, while specifically female perspectives were explored in the simultaneous study on the practices of fisherwomen by Manulevu et al. (2026).

BRUV-derived species records were subsequently compared with interview-derived species lists to assess congruence between ecological 'snapshot' observations and LEK. Using these two methods created a comprehensive and locally meaningful dataset which would not have been possible from either method alone.

Figure 1: Timeline of applied methods in this study.

2.1. Semi-structured interviews

We conducted 15 semi-structured interviews, comprising nine initial interviews and six follow-up interviews with a total of 9 knowledge holders, across four sites on Ovalau island. Free prior and informed consent (FPIC) was used for all methods. Participants were selected using purposive and snowball sampling to ensure inclusion of individuals with direct experience of reef passage use, including fishers, other community members, and knowledge holders. Community entry followed customary protocols with collective consent, including consultation with village leaders and adherence to local cultural practices. Interviewees also individually provided verbal free informed consent prior to participation. Interviews were carried out in Vatukalo Village, Levuka Town, Levuka Vakaviti, and Tokou Village (Table 1).

These semi-structured interviews were conducted in English and Fijian language between September and December 2025, in such a way that they were as close as possible to a 'natural' conversation. These conversations lasted between 30 and 75 minutes and were held in locations chosen by participants, including homes and community spaces. Notes were also taken during and after these interactions, and with participants' permission, four interviews were also audio-recorded.

Table 1: Number of interviewees per village.

Village	Vatukalo Village	Levuka Town	Levuka Vakaviti	Tokou Village
Initial Interview	4	1	1	3
Follow-up Interview	4	1	1	-

The interview guide (Attachment04) we developed focused on fishermen and was articulated around four thematic domains: (1) fishing grounds and practices, (2) knowledge of fish and marine environment, (3) local values of reef passages and fish, (4) perceptions of this research and advice for conducting underwater videos. This interview guide included both open and closed-ended questions, to allow flexibility in probing while maintaining comparability across participants (Adams, 2015). This approach was appropriate for eliciting narrative responses and capturing nuanced socio-ecological knowledge and practices related to reef passages.

2.2. Baited remote underwater videos (BRUV)

Sites were selected to represent commonly used fishing grounds and habitat types identified during semi-structured interviews. Deployments were conducted during both ebb and flow tides (Table 2), as interviewees indicated that there is more fish movement during these times.

Table 2: Number of recording sessions per tide and passage.

Passage	Toki Passage	Natubari Passage	Nalulu Passage
Ebb tide	2	2	1
Flow tide	3	1	1

We were unable to do more camera deployments in Toki passage on 26/11/2025 (Table 3) during ebb tide due to the depth sounder suddenly not working and we were not able to find a suitable depth. After multiple tries, we increased the rope to 90 meters, however the bottom still did not touch.

Deployment *A10_27112025_flow_natubari*, *S11_06122025_flow_toki* and *S11_08122025_ebb_nalulu* had technical issues and the camera stopped recording after autosaving the first 11 minutes, six minutes, and 14 minutes respectively (in yellow highlight). Deployments *D11_08122025_flow_nalulu* and *A10_08122025_flow_nalulu* is suspected to have overheated and turned off immediately after deployment and did not retain useful video footage (in red highlight).

Due to the depth sounder not working properly and/or fluctuating (turning on and off), we were unable to get an accurate depth measurement for most deployments on 27/11/2025.

We recommend carrying a second depth sounder or a secondary method to record depth in the event the depth sounder fails. After investigating the depth sounder failing, the reason being was the battery needed to be replaced. It returned to normal function after the battery was replaced for the deployments done 16/12/2025 onwards. We also recommend keeping a cooler or cool box to store the cameras when working in high UV / direct sunlight for multiple hours as this can overheat the camera and the batteries.

Table 3: BRUV deployments summary. Deployment ID is a concatenate of the camera name (S11, D11, A10, B10, A9), date of deployment, tidal phase, and reef passage. Yellow: certain technical issues. Red: Video not useful.

		Deployment ID	Tide	Depth deployed (meters)	Recording time after edit (minutes)	Deployment time
TokiPassage	1	S11_25112025_flow_toki	Flow	~25	34	1004
	2	D11_25112025_ebb_toki	Ebb	30	65	1402
	3	A10_25112025_ebb_toki	Ebb	30	49min31s	1423
	4	S11_26112025_ebb_toki	Ebb	17	37mins39s	1521
	5	A9_26112025_ebb_toki	Ebb	39.5	74	1527
	6	D11_26112025_flow_toki	Flow	20.5	59mins55s	1049
	7	A9_26112025_flow_toki	Flow	34.8	64	1058
	8	S11_26112025_flow_toki	Flow	64	65	1116
	9	B10_26112025_flow_toki	Flow	36.2	56mins24s	1126
	10	A10_26112025_flow_toki	Flow	60	67	1206
	11	A10_06122025_flow_toki	Flow	17.8	78	1608
	12	B10_06122025_flow_toki	Flow	20.8	72	1621
	13	S11_06122025_flow_toki	Flow	14.7	6	1629
NatubariPassage	1	B10_27112025_flow_natubari	Flow	~17	75	1000
	2	S11_27112025_flow_natubari	Flow	shallow	80	1018
	3	D11_27112025_flow_natubari	Flow	shallow	67	1033
	4	A10_27112025_flow_natubari	Flow	shallow	11	1040
	5	A9_27112025_flow_natubari	Flow	shallow	64	1053
	6	B10_27112025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	shallow	97	1455
	7	S11_27112025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	shallow	48	1501
	8	A9_27112025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	~30	69	1515
	9	A10_27112025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	~18	59mins28s	1519
	10	D11_27112025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	shallow	72	1527
	11	S11_06122025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	12	66	1209
	12	D11_06122025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	44.3	73	1224
	13	A10_06122025_ebb_natubari	Ebb	40	78	1234
NaluluPassage	1	S11_08122025_ebb_nalulu	Ebb	34.7	13	1052
	2	D11_08122025_ebb_nalulu	Ebb	28	43mins43s	1101
	3	A9_08122025_ebb_nalulu	Ebb	27.4	91	1121
	4	A10_08122025_ebb_nalulu	Ebb	17.8	88	1127
	5	B10_08122025_ebb_nalulu	Ebb	19.2	83	1133
	6	A9_08122025_flow_nalulu	Flow	34.4	90	1413
	7	S11_08122025_flow_nalulu	Flow	36.7	79	1417
	8	D11_08122025_flow_nalulu	Flow	32.8	3	1421
	9	B10_08122025_flow_nalulu	Flow	26	87	1426
	10	A10_08122025_flow_nalulu	Flow	9.5	0	1435

2.2.1 GoPro Camera Settings

GoPro model Hero 9 black, two GoPro Hero 10 Black, and two GoPro Hero 11 Black were the available devices for the BRUV surveys. It was observed that the GoPro Hero 9 Black retained the most battery after the surveys compared to the Hero 10 and Hero 11 which in some instances turned off after 10-30 minutes.

All cameras were preset to record videos in 1080 pixels (P) at 30 frames per second (FPS) to maximize battery life while maintaining high video resolution.

2.2.2 Video Analysis

Some videos were edited and cut for storage purposes; from the videos only the beginning of the deployment and end of the deployment were cut.

2.2.3 Interview and BRUV Data Analysis

The interviews were analyzed using Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel (version 2019).

We compiled local observations and knowledge of reef passages around Ovalau including their characteristics, fishing practices, seasonal patterns, and associated tabu or fishing restrictions into a table (Attachment01). This also contained all information of any reef passages and fishing areas, as well as other comments, mentioned by interviewees.

In parallel, we compiled a list of marine animals mentioned by all interviewees with associated English common name, Fijian local name, scientific name, IUCN Red List status, and reef passages where the species is observed and/or caught along with additional comments into a table (Attachment02).

After BRUV video annotations, all identified fishes were compiled according to associated reef passage, Fijian name, Taxonomy, English common name, IUCN Red List status, if the fishes were attracted to the bait (yes or no), if the fish bites the bait (yes or no), depth of deployment (in meters), tide of deployment (ebb or flow), current strength (low-strong; decided according to how much the BRUV frame undulates in the video), and habitat type (reef, reef-slope, open, rubble) (Attachment03).

During the results dissemination in Tokou Village, the community asked for a visual overview of the species of concern for management and awareness purposes, ones that were recorded from interviews and BRUVs. Following this request, we provided a poster showcasing the IUCN red list species present in the data (Attachment05).

Finally, we created a short video showcasing the BRUV footage for dissemination to local communities at the end of the project. It was uploaded to YouTube through the SOCPacific2R Project YouTube channel (Bishwa, 2025).

3. Sources & References

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